

POLAC JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND MANAGEMENT SCIENCES (PJSMS)

Vol. 3 No. 1 March, 2025

ISSN - Print: 2992-5009; Online: 2437-1246

Editor-in-Chief

Solomon Olubunmi, PhD

Editor

Samson Olowo Kolawole, PhD

Associate Editors

Vincent Okwudili Iweama, PhD

Nwachi Loveday Agwu, PhD

Ayogu Chiagolum Elochukwu

Shamsudeen Alhassan Musa

Sagir Lawal, PhD

Vahyala Adamu Tari, PhD

Ubong Evans Abraham, PhD

Kabiru Umar, PhD

Valentine Ayo Mebu, PhD

Ajene Sunday Apeh, PhD

Editorial Advisory Board

Prof. Benjamin Oladapo Olley,

Prof. Benjamin Oluwabunmi Omolayo

Prof. Mike Duru,

Prof. Abdullahi Hassan Gorondutse,

Prof. Hussaini Tukur Hassan,

Prof. Junaidu Muhammad Kurawa

Prof. Canice Esidene Erunke,

Prof. Ahmad Audu Maiyaki,

Prof. Zubairu Kwambo Dagona,

Prof. Abu Maji,

Dr Bello Halilu Rogo,

Dr Abdulrazaq Ibrahim

Effectiveness of Manpower Training on Mathematics Teaching Anxiety Among Newly Employed Primary School Teachers in Lagos State

POLAC Journal of
Social and Management Sciences
2025, Vol. 3 (1), 45 – 50
©Faculty of Social and Management Sciences
Nigeria Police Academy, Kano.
pjsms@gmail.com
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15795430

¹Anthony Akinyemi Ayeobasan & ²Nwakaego Ihuoma Nwoke

¹Department of Educational Psychology, Federal College of Education (Technical), Akoka, Lagos. 08062723947, 08023643171

²Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Federal College of Education (Technical), Akoka, Lagos. 07017707395

Email:

Abstract

The study investigates the effectiveness of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety among newly employed primary school teachers in Lagos State. The participants in the study comprised 180 (90 male & 90 female) newly employed primary school teachers who were selected through stratified sampling using gender. The mathematics teaching anxiety rating scale was developed, validated and administered as a pre- and post-test assessment. Two research questions were raised, and two research hypotheses were generated to guide the study. The research design was quasi-experimental, and the data generated were analyzed using inferential statistics (t-test). There was a significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety among participants in the experimental groups. Similarly, there was a significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety across gender among participants in the experimental groups; consequently, the two hypotheses were rejected at ($p < 0.05$). Discussions based on the findings of the study were made and the following recommendations were put forward: manpower training has proved to be effective in enhancing mathematics teaching anxiety. Hence, stakeholders should increase the frequency of training among teachers, especially the newly employed ones. Newly employed female teachers should be given more priority in training and re-training programmes.

Keywords: Manpower, Teaching Anxiety & Mathematics Anxiety

Article history:

Received: 29 September 2024

Reviewed: 20 January 2025

Accepted: 29 March 2025

About the Journal: PJSMS is a multidisciplinary journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil-Kano, Nigeria, published biannually.

Ayeobasan, A. A. & Nwoke, N. I.

Effectiveness of Manpower Training on Mathematics Teaching Anxiety Among Newly Employed Primary School Teachers in Lagos State**Introduction**

Curriculum designed for primary schools in Nigeria encompasses all the subjects to be taught by the in-service trained teachers who have been trained for expected knowledge in each of the subjects during the training, hence there is no subject specification. Therefore, it becomes necessary for primary school teachers not only to demonstrate the mastery of each subject content but also to elicit the necessary courage and skills needed to teach, especially in mathematics. However, among all the available subjects in primary schools, mathematics has been a major point of concern not only to the teachers but also the in-service trained teachers, this might be as a result of some expected level of affective traits emanating from deficient in conceptual knowledge leading to lower self belief about their ability to master and teach the subject. Mohan (2021) corroborated that mathematics possesses the ability to stimulate feelings of anxiety, fear and helplessness. Hence, mathematics anxiety becomes a major emotional problem not only among the primary school pupils but also among the teachers, especially on teaching the subject to the students.

Asiedu (2020) defined Mathematics Teaching Anxiety (MTA) as the sensation of nervousness, apprehension and fear by teachers in the course of instruction of mathematical concepts, theories, formulas or problem-solving approach. In a similar vein, Brown (2019) viewed Mathematics Teaching Anxiety as the signal of how a person evaluates his competence to effectively and efficiently communicate with and engage children in mathematics interactions. Brown (2023) asserted that MTA can be triggered by various factors with further findings of Brown (2021) include lack of subject matter, inadequate training, fear of students

evaluation and classroom management, these revealed a significant association between mathematics teaching anxiety and mathematics anxiety as significant number of pre-service training teachers who manifested mathematics anxiety also exhibit mathematics teaching anxiety.

Obasanya (2018) submitted that MTA of teachers is consequential and it is capable of not only affecting the teachers but also the students and the whole teaching process. He further posited that mathematics-anxious teachers are capable of producing mathematics-anxious students. Sloan (2020) corroborated this by expatiated that teachers who possess higher levels of anxiety could unconsciously transmit their negative feelings, avoidance and fear of mathematics to students in as much as mathematics anxiety is associated with how instruction on mathematics is passed across. Although there is a rarity of literature on gender differences in Mathematics Teaching Anxiety, for instance, Dane (2005) in Akanbi (2019) found that gender did not moderate mathematics teaching anxiety, Ayandokun (2021) also found no significant difference due to gender among primary school teachers. Similarly, Asiedu (2020) did not find statistically significant interaction effects between pre-service teachers' mathematics anxiety and biases associated with students' gender. On the contrary, Birenbaum (2018) found gender differences with respect to mathematics anxiety across genders among pre-service teachers.

Training is a crucial medium to enhance quality assurance, as it strengthens the competence and confidence of individuals in attaining effective and efficient outcomes. Globally, organisations devote a significant portion of their funds and staff time to training

with the expectation of improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the programme. Training and development are fundamental to enhancing employee performance and organizational success in the educational sector. Effective training programmes can improve Teachers' technical skills, students/teachers relationships, as well as overall job competence. Armstrong (2021) emphasizes that investment in teachers' manpower training leads to increased productivity, better service delivery, and higher job satisfaction, and teachers who often interact directly with students require consistent development in essential areas of need to adapt to new experiences to improve the standard of delivery.

Recent research supports the notion that training and development positively impact job performance. For instance, a study by Joel (2020) indicates that teachers who participate in targeted training programmes exhibit improved performance and greater job efficiency. This is particularly relevant in Lagos State, especially among the newly employed teachers with varying challenges characterized by high demand for expertise, knowledge and professionalism in delivering exceptional services. Armstrong (2021) corroborates Joel (2020) that well-structured manpower training not only enhances skills among newly employed teachers but also motivates and commits teachers to their roles. Despite the benefits, implementing effective training programmes among Lagos State teachers, especially the newly employed, has faced several challenges, which include financial constraints, limited resources, and competent training experts, and these have been significant barriers to comprehensive training, as noted by Obinna (2023). Additionally, resistance to changes and cultural factors may impact the acceptance and effectiveness of training initiatives, as highlighted by Adeniran (2023). Hence, there

is a need to address these challenges to maximise the benefits of training and ensure that staff development efforts yield the desired outcomes among newly employed teachers and teachers in Lagos State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. Is there a significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores among participants in the experimental groups?
2. Is there any significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores across gender among participants in the experimental groups?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores among participants in the experimental groups.
2. There is no significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores across gender among participants in the experimental group.

Method

The study adopted a quasi-experimental, separate sample pre-test/post-test control group design. It consists of two groups: one training group and one control. Quasi-experimental design was appropriate because it involves human behaviour and does not permit randomization of subjects and control of all variables (Nwadinigwe, 2002). The researcher adopted a training manual on Mathophobia in Mathematics Teaching by Joel (2020) and also developed a Mathematics Teaching Anxiety Rating Scale, which was validated using the test-retest method after a

three-week interval. The reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained after correlation, and this was considered adequate for the study. The study sample comprised 180 (90 male & 90 female) newly employed primary school teachers in Lagos State, and the sampling procedure was a multi-stage sampling technique. All the participants were put into two strata using gender (90 male and 90 female). A random sampling technique was adopted to select 45 males and 45 females to form two groups of 90 participants per group. One group was randomly assigned to training and the other assigned to control. The training session last 4 weeks, Mathematics Teaching Anxiety Rating Scale was administered as pre-test in the first week across the experimental groups, manual on Mathophobia in Mathematics Teaching was employed as a guide in the 4 weeks training for the training group while the Control group was administered placebo, the training group received training of 2 hours for 3 days in a week spanning four weeks. The Teaching Anxiety Rating Scale was also administered in the 6th week as a post-test across the groups.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores among participants in the experimental groups.

Table 1: T-Test analysis for experimental groups

Group	N	\bar{X}	S^2	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Training	90	34.80	5.21	178	0.23	0.13	P<0.05
Control	90	26.20	4.18				

P<0.05; df =178; crt-t = 0.13

Since the t-calculated value of 0.23 is greater than the t-critical of 0.13, it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety among participants. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no

significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety among participants, is rejected, and the alternative is upheld.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores across gender among participants in the experimental group.

Table 2: T-test analysis for experimental groups across gender

Group	N	\bar{X}	S^2	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	45	43.2	6.11	178	0.22	0.14	P<0.05
Female	45	36.8	4.91				

P<0.05; df =178; crt-t = 0.14

Since the t-calculated of 0.22 is greater than the t-critical of 0.14, it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety across gender among participants.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores among participants in the experimental groups. The post-test mean scores of the training group were 34.80, while the control group had a post-test mean score of 26.20. This revelation aligned with the findings of Akinwale (2023), who discovered a similar influence of in-service training on job productivity among selected primary school teachers in Epe.

Manpower training exhibits a significant effect on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores among newly employed primary school teachers in the training group. This finding concurred with the submission of Aliya (2021), which stated that the training of personnel has a positive relationship with productivity among skilled workers. However, Birenbaum (2018) found no significant relationship between productivity trained and non-trained teachers among secondary school teachers.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores across gender among participants in the experimental groups. Male participants had a higher post-test mean score of 43.2 compared to the 36.8 post-test mean score of the female; this finding concurred with the findings of Brown (2019), which stated that male participants performed better than female counterparts in psychomotor skills among selected secondary school teachers. Similarly, Omale (2020) in his findings established that males had higher ability and capacity to attain maximum productivity compared to their female counterparts when exposed to some intervention.

Conclusion

In light of the preceding discussions, the following conclusions were drawn;

1. There was a significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores among participants in the experimental groups.
2. There was a significant effect of manpower training on mathematics teaching anxiety post-test scores across gender among participants in the experimental group.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are put forward:

1. Since manpower training has proved to be effective in enhancing mathematics teaching anxiety. Hence, the stakeholders should earmark more funds and increase the frequency of training among teachers, especially the newly employed ones.
2. Newly employed female teachers should be given more priority on training and re-training programmes since the findings of this study revealed less effect on the dependent variable.

References

- Adeniran, A. L. (2023). *Manpower training manual*. Lagos, Ajumobi Publishers.
- Akanbi, L. B. (2019). Gender as predictor of mathematics anxiety among selected secondary students. *Journal of Educational Studies*, 3(2) 11-23
- Akinwande, B. M. (2023). Influence of structured training and job satisfaction among teachers in Ondo State. *Journal of Vocational Education*, 3(2) 11-22
- Aliya, D. F. (2021). Effectiveness of training on hospitality industry. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism*, 4(3) 26-37.
- Armstrong, M. M. (2021). Employee motivation and engagement through training programmes. *Workforce Development Quarterly*, 19(2) 134-150
- Asiedu, A. A. (2020). Relationship between training and performance among teachers. *Journal of Social Science Education*, 2(4) 23-32
- Ayandokun, P. M. (2021) *Educational psychology practice*, Ibadan, Godson Publishers.
- Birenbaum (2018). Gender as correlates of anxiety in testing among secondary school students in Lagos State. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 3(2) 18-27
- Brown, W. S. (2019). *Fundamentals of goal setting and task performance*. Lagos Rex Publishers.
- Joel, A. A. (2020). *Efficacy of training*. Awka Junet Publishers.
- Mohan, B. S. (2021). Teachers' qualifications as predictors of affective traits among secondary school students. *Journal of Vocational and Business Education*, 3(1) 14-22
- Nwadinigwe, I. P. (2002). *Fundamentals of research methods and statistics*. Ibadan: Sibon Books Ltd.

- Obasanya, M. D. (2018). Review of information on the benefits of training for employers. *Journals of Business Education*, 3(1) 20-29
- Obinna, E. U. (2023). *Principles of Human Resources*: Lagos, Jet Printers.
- Omale, U. F. (2020). Influence of in-service training on science teachers in Lagos State. *Journal of Science Education*, 1(3) 22-30
- Sloan (2020). Effects of affective factors on learning outcomes in mathematics among secondary school students. *Lagos Journal of Education Review*, 3(4)6-17
- Sloan, P. P. (2020). The impact of training on social services. *Journal of Social Science Education*, 2(2) 11-23